

Soil organic compounds determination by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry

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Soil is a heterogeneous system of great structural and functional complexity that acts as a regulatory center for numerous ecosystem processes. Soil organic matter is a complex mixture of biological material derived from a variety of sources, including microorganisms, plants, fungi, and animals. These materials undergo a series of degradation and transformation processes, resulting in a heterogeneous mixture of compounds that play a vital role in soil formation and functioning.

Extraction with organic solvents is used to isolate a lipid fraction containing hydrophobic organic compounds from soil. The composition of this fraction varies from complex esterified structures such as phospholipids, glycolipids, and sphingolipids to simpler molecules such as aliphatic acids, alcohols, aldehydes, and ketones [1].

Basic methodological approaches for determining organic compounds in soils typically involve several sequential steps: extraction, fractionation, chemical modification, identification, and quantitative analysis using chromatographic methods [2].

The classic method for extracting lipid components from soil is the Soxhlet method, but its use is complicated by several drawbacks, including the lengthy extraction process, high solvent consumption, and the potential for distortion of the qualitative and quantitative composition of the sample. Some of these problems can be solved using modern extraction methods, including accelerated solvent extraction (ASE). The use of the ASE method allows for automation and significant acceleration of the extraction of organic compounds from solid matrices, as well as minimizing the likelihood of distortion of the sample's component composition.

The complexity and multicomponent composition of the resulting soil extracts requires the use of chromatograph mass spectrometry for their analysis. However, even in this case, prior to instrumental analysis, preliminary fractionation of the target components by adsorption chromatography is necessary. Chemical modification methods also improve the reliability of qualitative and quantitative analysis of soil organic compounds. Changing the chemical nature of the analyzed compounds improves the stability of the resulting analytical forms, as well as the selectivity and sensitivity of their determination.

In the chromatograph mass spectrometry method, derivatization is used to increase the signal intensity of the molecular (characteristic) ion, as well as to increase the specificity of fragmentation of analytes, which ensures their more reliable identification.

The potential for using lipid components as marker compounds for various studies in soil science has not yet been fully explored, and therefore this area, including its analytical component, continues to actively develop.

References

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